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A novel tool to define the population structure of species, called MSTclust

Extract from the preprint article:

A dual barcoding approach to bacterial strain nomenclature: Genomic taxonomy of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* strains | bioRxiv.

Melanie Hennart, Julien Guglielmini, Martin C.J. Maiden, Keith A. Jolley, Alexis Criscuolo, Sylvain Brisse. bioRxiv 2021.07.26.453808;
doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.07.26.453808>

A pairwise dissimilarity between two cgMLST profiles can be defined by the proportion of loci with two distinct alleles among the loci where alleles are defined in both profiles. A pairwise dissimilarity matrix can be computed from n cgMLST profiles, and can be used to build a minimum spanning tree (MStree; e.g., Kruskal, 1956; Prim, 1957a; Dijkstra, 1959), allowing to infer a clustering of the cgMLST profiles, defined by the k different connected components obtained by removing from the MStree all edges of length larger than a specified threshold t . Such an MStree-based clustering is closely related to the single-linkage classification of the n cgMLST profiles (e.g., Gower and Ross, 1969; Johnson, 1967).

In order to determine optimal thresholds t , several criteria can be used. Among these criteria, the average silhouette coefficient S_t assesses the ability of an MStree-based clustering to consistently represents in k class(es) the 'natural' grouping of the cgMLST profiles (Rousseeuw, 1987; Lengyel and Botta-Dukát, 2019). When S_t is close to 1, the clustering can be considered as accurate. A confidence interval for S_t can be also obtained by considering the distribution of the average silhouette coefficients of different clustering computed from the distance matrix with 'noised' entries.

Further, in order to assess whether an MStree-based clustering C_t (using threshold t) is robust to any subsampling biases, a simple approach is to build another MStree-based clustering C'_t from a subsample of cgMLST profiles, and to measure the agreement between the cgMLST profile partitions induced by C'_t and C_t . When the level of agreement remains high for different subsampling rates, the corresponding threshold t can be considered as being leading to stable clustering. Among different agreement metrics between partitions, the second adjusted Wallace coefficient w (Wallace, 1983; Severiano et al., 2011) estimates the probability of observing a pair of profiles in the same class in C_t when they are clustered in the same class in C'_t . In order to derive a single coefficient W_t from a range of different subsampling rates r (= 10% to 90%), different coefficients w were estimated and averaged for each rate r , the area under the resulting curve (i.e., rates r on X-axis; coefficient w on Y-axis) was computed and normalized (using its maximum expected value). Such a normalized area W_t is close to 1 when the different adjusted Wallace coefficients w (i.e., derived from varying subsampling rates) are all close to their maximum value, therefore showing that the corresponding MStree-based clustering (based on the threshold t) is robust to any subsampling biases. A confidence interval for W_t can be also obtained using the same approach as for S_t (see above).

The MStree-based clustering of cgMLST profiles, as well as the two consistency and stability indices S_t and W_t were implemented in the tool MSTclust (<https://gitlab.pasteur.fr/GIPhy/MSTclust>). For more details, please see <https://gitlab.pasteur.fr/GIPhy/MSTclust/-/blob/0.21b/Technical.Notes.pdf>.

Example for the dataset of *K. pneumoniae* strains used in the article

To determine optimal allelic mismatch thresholds that would reflect the Kp population structure, the consistency and stability properties of single-linkage clustering groups were assessed for every threshold value t from 1 to 629 allelic mismatches. The Silhouette coefficient S_t had a plateau of optimal values in the range corresponding to 118/629 (18.8%) to 355/629 (56.4%) allelic mismatches (**Figure 1**,

blue curve). Analysis of the stability to subsampling (W_t ; based on an adjusted Wallace coefficient; Figure 1, green curve) identified several ranges of allelic mismatch threshold values that were associated to maximal stability.

Figure 1. Distribution of pairwise cgMLST distances, clustering properties and phylogenetic congruence. Values are plotted for the 7,060 genomes dataset. Threshold values (t) are shown on the X-axis, corresponding to allelic profile mismatch values up to 629 (or 100%). Grey histograms: distribution of pairwise allelic mismatches. The curves represent the consistency (silhouette) and stability coefficients S_t (blue) and W_t (green), respectively, obtained with each threshold t ; the corresponding scale is on the left Y-axis. The dotted vertical red lines at $t = 43/629$, $190/629$, $585/629$ and $610/629$ represent the thresholds that correspond to clonal groups, sublineages, phylogroups and species, respectively.

The above analyses led us to propose four deep classification levels. The two first thresholds, 610 and 585 allelic mismatches, enable species and subspecies separations, respectively. We next defined a threshold at the level of 190 allelic mismatches, corresponding to the optimal combination of consistency and stability coefficients S_t and W_t . The single-linkage clustering based on this threshold created 705 groups, which we define as 'sublineages' (SL). By design, this threshold separated into distinct groups, the pairs of genomes corresponding to the major mode (at 520 mismatches), *i.e.*, the majority of genomes that have distinct STs within phylogroups. Finally, a threshold of 43 allelic mismatches was defined to separate genome pairs of the 79-mismatch mode. This value corresponded to local optima of both S_t and W_t coefficients. Interestingly, this threshold value was also located in the optimal range of compatibility with the classical 7-gene ST definitions (Rand index $R_t \geq 0.70$ was observed for $10 \leq t \leq 51$). The use of this threshold resulted in 1,147 groups, which we propose to define as 'clonal groups' (CG).

References:

- Dijkstra, E.W. (1959). A note on two problems in connexion with graphs. *Numer. Math.* 1, 269–271.
- Gower, J.C., and Ross, G.J.S. (1969). Minimum Spanning Trees and Single Linkage Cluster Analysis. *Appl. Stat.* 18, 54.
- Johnson, S.C. (1967). Hierarchical clustering schemes. *Psychometrika* 32, 241–254.
- Kruskal, J.B. (1956). On the shortest spanning subtree of a graph and the traveling salesman problem. *Proc. Am. Math. Soc.* 7, 48–48.

Lengyel, A., and Botta-Dukát, Z. (2019). Silhouette width using generalized mean—A flexible method for assessing clustering efficiency. *Ecol. Evol.* 9, 13231–13243.

Prim, R.C. (1957). Shortest Connection Networks And Some Generalizations. *Bell Syst. Tech. J.* 36, 1389–1401.

Rousseeuw, P.J. (1987). Silhouettes: A graphical aid to the interpretation and validation of cluster analysis. *J. Comput. Appl. Math.* 20, 53–65.

Severiano, A., Pinto, F.R., Ramirez, M., and Carriço, J.A. (2011). Adjusted Wallace Coefficient as a Measure of Congruence between Typing Methods. *J. Clin. Microbiol.* 49, 3997–4000.

Wallace, D.L. (1983). A Method for Comparing Two Hierarchical Clusterings: Comment. *J. Am. Stat. Assoc.* 78, 569–576.